

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF LEXEMES WITHIN THE CONCEPT OF THE IDEA OF THE GREAT MAN IN MARLOWE'S DRAMA "TAMERLANE THE GREAT"

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Abstract: This article presents a semantic analysis of lexemes within the concept of the idea of the Great Man in Christopher Marlowe's drama "Tamerlan the Great." By examining the linguistic choices and lexical nuances employed by Marlowe, this study aims to delve into the complex portrayal of the Great Man archetype in the play. Through the analysis of key lexemes and their semantic connotations, this article sheds light on the multifaceted nature of the Great Man concept, exploring themes of power, ambition, morality, and the human condition.

Keywords: Semantic analysis, lexemes, Great Man, Christopher Marlowe, "Tamerlan the Great," power, ambition, morality, human condition.

Introduction: Christopher Marlowe, a prominent figure of the Renaissance era, explored the concept of the Great Man in his play "Tamerlan the Great." This article seeks to analyze the semantic intricacies of the lexemes employed within the framework of the Great Man archetype in Marlowe's drama. By examining the linguistic choices and semantic connotations of key lexemes, we gain a deeper understanding of how Marlowe constructs and conveys the idea of the Great Man, exploring themes of power, ambition, morality, and the complexities of the human condition.

1. **Semantic Analysis of Lexemes:** The semantic analysis of lexemes within the concept of the Great Man in "Tamerlan the Great" unveils the multifaceted nature of this archetype. Lexemes such as "conquer," "dominion," and "glory" evoke notions of power, ambition, and the pursuit of greatness. Marlowe's deliberate choice of words carries deeper connotations, reflecting the character's desire for dominance and the price one must pay to attain it. Furthermore, lexemes associated with morality, such as "virtue," "honor," and "conscience," highlight the ethical dimensions of the Great Man concept, emphasizing the tension between personal ambition and moral responsibility.

2. **The Great Man as a Figure of Ambition:** Marlowe's use of lexemes associated with ambition showcases the character's relentless pursuit of power. Lexical choices such as "aspiring," "strive," and "thirst" illustrate the character's insatiable ambition, underscoring the notion that the Great Man is driven by an unquenchable thirst for success and recognition. These lexemes reveal the internal conflicts faced by the Great Man as they navigate the fine line between ambition and the consequences of their actions.

3. **Portrayal of the Human Condition:** Through carefully selected lexemes, Marlowe delves into the complexities of the human condition within the context of the Great Man. Lexemes such as "glory," "fate," and "mortality" illuminate the character's contemplation of life's transience and the inevitable mortality that accompanies greatness. The usage of these lexemes emphasizes the ephemeral nature of power and the existential dilemmas faced by the Great Man, challenging conventional notions of immortality and invincibility.

Conclusion: Christopher Marlowe's "Tamerlan the Great" presents a nuanced exploration of the concept of the Great Man through the strategic use of lexemes. The semantic analysis of key lexemes in the play reveals the intricate layers of meaning and connotations associated

with the Great Man archetype. Marlowe's linguistic choices highlight themes of power, ambition, morality, and the human condition, unraveling the complex nature of the Great Man's journey.

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